

Reconstruction of the near-surface temperature field in southern Germany: data, methods, patterns

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Keywords: Near-surface geothermal energy, temperature data analysis, Geothermal Information System (GeotIS), kriging / geostatistics, geothermal potential mapping

Abstract

To systematically assess Germany's near-surface geothermal potential and support the energy transition through an expanded geothermal database, the Wärmegut project, conducted in cooperation with the Geological Surveys, collects and evaluates geothermally relevant information, integrating them into the Geothermal Information System (GeotIS), originally designed for deep geothermal applications. Based on about 3,000 measurements from more than 1,500 wells in Rhineland-Palatinate and Baden-Württemberg, this paper presents a methodology to reconstruct the near-surface temperature field. The shallow temperature-elevation regression line is used as a Kriging drift term to capture the strong influence of topography and is extended to include surface sealing effects. The analysis focuses on 50 m depth as a reference level, independent of seasonal variations, providing a baseline relevant for shallow geothermal applications and subsequent studies. Two complementary approaches are applied: extending satellite-based land surface temperatures using bottom-hole temperatures, and independent evaluation of temperature logs. A correction procedure further allows the use of extraction logs, whether operational or shut-in logs which are affected by prior pumping, to estimate the undisturbed subsurface temperature field.

1. Introduction

The Geothermal Information System (GeotIS), along with the FIS-GP database, acts as a freely accessible central reference, providing a comprehensive compilation of geothermally relevant data, including well temperature logs, thermal rock properties, and hydrogeological information. The database currently contains temperature data from approximately 11,000 wells (10,500 in Germany), with a primary focus on the deep temperature field (Agemar et al. 2012). To complement this, the database is being extended with near-surface temperature information along two parallel lines: the evaluation of satellite-based land surface temperatures (Holstein et al., in press) and, addressed in this study, the analysis of shallow temperature logs, which are further interpolated using Kriging. In doing so, GeotIS extends its role in supporting project planning and research for shallow geothermal applications, complementing its established use for deep geothermal energy and contributing to the energy transition.

The data acquisition for this study is carried out within the Wärmegut project, a nationwide initiative conducted in cooperation with all German Geological Surveys. Recently, a national "traffic-light map" was created, providing both professionals and private users with a quick overview of where shallow geothermal drilling is permitted, subject to conditions, or prohibited. The reconstruction of the near-surface temperature field presented in this work aims to support the assessment of geothermal potentials, for instance within modelling frameworks such as GEO-HANDlight (Miocic et al., 2024).

In previous analyses of deeper temperature logs, one main focus was on correcting the effects of prior drilling activities (Agemar et al., 2012). In contrast, the present study concentrates on the shallow subsurface with particular emphasis on 50 m depth as a reference level, since it is relevant for shallow geothermal systems and largely unaffected by seasonal variations. While drilling-related effects may still play a role at shallow depths, other influences appear to be more dominant, including topography, land use, and groundwater flow, as well as previous operations and past climate variations. These factors likely account for most of the observed variability and therefore require explicit consideration.

The following sections describe the development of a methodology towards the derivation of a national shallow temperature field. Section 2 introduces the datasets from Baden-Württemberg and Rhineland-Palatinate, which form the basis for the development and evaluation of the methodology. Section 3 presents a rapid evaluation method that extends satellite-based land surface temperatures with bottom-hole temperatures. A temperature-elevation regression line including a shallow geothermal gradient is then used for Kriging. This approach is demonstrated using the dataset from Baden-Württemberg. Section 4 introduces a dedicated visualization and analysis tool, used to derive the temperature field for Rhineland-Palatinate from an in-depth analysis of temperature logs, independent of land surface temperatures. The results from a multiple regression analysis and kriging highlight and compare the influence of topography and urbanization on the shallow temperature field. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the results obtained with both datasets.

2. Data basis

The well-log datasets used to develop the methodology for deriving the shallow temperature field were provided by the Geological Surveys of Baden-Württemberg (LGRB) and Rhineland-Palatinate (LGB-RLP). They comprise approximately 2,300 logs from 1,200 wells and 700 logs from 360 wells, respectively. Considering the size of each state, the average well density in the dataset from Baden-Württemberg is about twice that of Rhineland-Palatinate (Fig. 1). In both datasets, data density is uneven, with clusters of boreholes in some regions and large areas without measurements. Well-covered regions include the Upper Rhine Graben and the Neckar region in Baden-Württemberg, as well as the Palatinate Forest, parts of the Mainz Basin, the Saar–Nahe Basin, and the Westerwald in Rhineland-Palatinate. Coverage is sparse in northeastern Baden-Württemberg, the higher elevations of the Black Forest and Swabian Alb, and the Eifel region in Rhineland-Palatinate, except at Lake Laach. Despite regional differences, both datasets are extensive and representative for the purpose of this study. In general, most wells are located in lowland areas, which is advantageous for the analysis because these regions exhibit the greatest variability, particularly with respect to urbanization.

The wells are of different types, including those for groundwater extraction (drinking, mineral, and brewing water) as well as for exploration and research purposes. The logs originate from various measurement campaigns conducted since the 1950s. The variability within the dataset can be considered advantageous from a statistical perspective, as it increases the representativeness of the overall sample. The logs include both shut-in and operational conditions, the latter representing groundwater extraction with only few exceptions. In both datasets, single (predominantly shut-in) logs occur in approximately 40% of wells, while wells with more than two logs make up roughly 10%. The remainder have two logs, almost always one shut-in and one operational.

Concerning land surface data, a temperature field combining Landsat 8 (USGS, 2025b) and MODIS (Wan et al., 2021) satellite data was used, as described in detail by Holstein et al. (in press). Landsat 8 provides two measurements per month between 2013 and 2024, with a high spatial resolution of 100 m. The merging was performed to overcome the limited temporal resolution of

Landsat, as MODIS offers two measurements per day over the same period, but at a lower spatial resolution of 1000 m. Surface sealing was derived from the land use model LBM-DE2021 (BKG, 2021). To account for the influence of adjacent land use on the temperature field, the sealing value at each borehole location was averaged over a radius of 100 m. The digital elevation model (used, for example, in Fig. 1) was obtained from the USGS EarthExplorer platform (USGS, 2025b).

Fig. 1: Coverage of temperature logs in a) Baden-Württemberg and b) Rhineland-Palatinate.

3. Surface-to-subsurface temperature extrapolation

The methodology was developed and tested using the dataset from Baden-Württemberg. It represents a rapid evaluation approach designed to extend land surface temperature information into the subsurface. The approach is based on a linear interpolation between the land surface temperature and the deepest measured temperature at each well (bottom-hole temperature), followed by spatial interpolation. This concept is motivated by the fact that land surface temperature provides a comprehensive upper boundary condition that can be measured over large areas, while the bottom-hole temperature represents the most reliable temperature measurement within a well, as it is largely unaffected by previous groundwater extraction. The result is a three-dimensionally extrapolated temperature field in which the influence of well observations increases with depth while the impact of satellite-based land surface temperature decreases.

Figure 2a provides an overview of the land surface temperatures and bottom-hole temperatures exceeding the reference depth of 50 m, which were therefore included in the analysis applying the methodology presented in this section. Approximately 480 of the 1,200 wells from Baden-Württemberg reach the considered depth and were used in this analysis. Around 150 of these are only slightly deeper (within 20 m below the reference depth) and therefore exert a dominant influence on the interpolation relative to the land surface temperature. Another 150 wells do not exceed 100 m in depth. About 180 wells are considerably deeper, resulting in a stronger influence of land surface temperatures on the calculated field. Results dominated by well observations are considered more reliable, since atmospheric effects are negligible at the reference depth of 50 m,

except for long-term climatic variations. In most regions, bottom-hole temperatures are shallower than 100 m, whereas deeper wells where land surface temperatures exert a stronger control are mainly located in the Swabian Alb (green area in Fig. 2b, the northern Alpine Foothills (brown) and the southern Black Forest (orange).

Fig. 2: Surface-to-subsurface temperature extrapolation: a) Land surface temperatures (LST), used well locations for bottom hole temperature (BHT) grouped by depth; b) Best-fit line for 50 m subsurface temperature versus elevation (colours denote main geological units).

3.1 Effect of topography

By examining correlations, we found that temperatures in the shallow subsurface depend most clearly on topography, whereas the influence of land use, groundwater flow, and other factors is less pronounced. Therefore, Fig. 2b illustrates the impact of topography, represented by land surface elevation, on temperatures observed in wells at shallow depth (50 m). Temperatures are high for instance in the low elevated parts of the Gaeu geological unit (orchid colour in Fig. 2b) and decrease to below 10 °C in the higher regions of the Black Forest (orange) and the Swabian Alb (green). The data show a high degree of scatter ($R^2 = 0.3$), which can be attributed to the effects of land use, (surface sealing), e.g. at Stuttgart (Keuper Uplands, purple), groundwater flow, and local anomalies known from analyses at greater depths (Schellschmidt and Stober, 2008), particularly in the Upper Rhine Graben (black color) and at Bad Urach and Bad Boll (Voralb, red).

While Figure 2 demonstrated that the effect of topography can be approximately represented by a linear fit of temperature versus land surface elevation for the reference depth of 50 m, Fig. 3 shows how the best-fit line varies with depth. The plotted bars indicate the number of borehole observations at each depth, showing that sufficient data are available for the upper shallow depths, with the effective threshold lying approximately between 100 and 200 m. The slope of the regression line at the land surface is close to the atmospheric lapse rate (≈ 6 K/km, ICAO, 1993). With increasing depth, the slope becomes steeper and necessarily approaches the deep geothermal gradient (Sobh et al. 2025), since temperature differences between two absolute elevations are considered.

Figure 3b illustrates the general behaviour observed in the present study that the slope of temperature versus land surface elevation increases with depth, starting at the atmospheric lapse rate. The analysed well logs also reveal regional variations in slope, indicating that it depends on the local geological conditions (e.g., topographic features, rock type, groundwater flow) and that it represents an average value for the area well logs are evaluated from. Therefore, the slope from the regression analysis can be interpreted as an average shallow geothermal gradient for the considered region (in this section the entire state of Baden-Württemberg). The slope increases with depth according to the prevailing geological conditions.

Fig. 3: Shallow geothermal gradient: a) Increase of best-fit slope (shallow geothermal gradient) with depth; b) General behaviour as intermediate between the atmospheric temperature gradient (lapse rate) and the deep (topography-independent) geothermal gradient.

3.2 Kriging with external drift

The variogram of residual temperatures (deviations from the topography-related trend) at the reference depth of 50 m shows that spatial correlation declines over a range of 25 km (Fig. 4). Over such distances, land surface elevation varies by several hundred meters in many areas of Baden-Württemberg. Therefore, the temperature–elevation regression line was used as a drift (trend) in the kriging interpolation. The procedure is as follows: first, the effect of topography is removed from the borehole measurements using the best-fit regression line, including the shallow geothermal gradient, resulting in residual temperatures. Kriging interpolation is then performed for a reference elevation of 0 m a.s.l. Finally, the topographic effect is reintroduced according to the land surface elevation at each grid point of the interpolation. This approach improves the interpolation compared to models in which topography is not explicitly considered.

As expected, the kriging results reflect the influence of topography (Fig. 4). In particular, temperatures in the Stuttgart area are higher than the trend, indicating a pronounced urban heat island effect. Elevated temperatures extend over a broader region, including the area of Bad Urach and Bad Boll, where geothermal anomalies occur due to higher heat fluxes. (Schellschmidt and Stober, 2008). Temperatures are also higher than the trend in the southern Upper Rhine Graben, whereas they are lower in its central and northern parts within Baden-Württemberg.

Fig. 4: Kriging interpolation using best-fit line (temperature at 50 m depth with respect to land surface elevation) as external trend: a) Variogram for residual temperature (deviation from trend); b) Temperature at 50 m depth; c) Drift (trend) temperature; d) Residuals (crosses mark well locations).

4. Subsurface log analysis

The methodology was developed and tested using the dataset from Rhineland-Palatinate. It involves an in-depth analysis of well logs and is independent of land surface temperature data. Out of the 360 available wells, 260 were selected for analysis because they include temperature measurements at the reference depth of 50 m, comprising about 530 logs, at least 250 of which were recorded under shut-in conditions. Among the remaining wells, approximately 50 are shallower than 50 m, whereas about 25 are deeper but lack temperature data at the reference depth.

4.1 Log visualization and analysis tool

An interactive tool was developed in Python with Bokeh for browser-based interactivity to enable efficient analysis of well logs, their interdependence, and their relationships with neighbouring well logs (Fig. 5). It was created during the log analysis process and is continuously extended to provide and store information that proves relevant during the analysis, such as elevation, land use at the borehole location, and quality-related data from the logs, including inflow and outflow zones and rates, casing, lithology, shut-in and previous operation times, all derived from borehole measurement reports accessible through the tool. Evaluation points are defined along the well logs for use in further analyses, such as stochastic evaluations, and in the Kriging interpolation. The results are stored in a PostgreSQL database, ensuring that all relevant information from the well logs is readily available and dynamically updated for ongoing analyses.

Fig. 5: Visualization and analysis tool for temperature logs: a) Interface displaying quality-relevant information, allowing data points (black dots) to be set along the logs, e.g. for subsequent kriging interpolation; b) Correction of groundwater extraction, with the grey line indicating the corrected temperature profile T^* .

4.2 Handling extraction and post-extraction temperature logs

The analysis focuses on logs recorded during shut-in periods. However, it was often uncertain whether a log declared as measured under shut-in conditions was actually in equilibrium with the undisturbed subsurface temperature field or still affected by previous operations, most commonly

groundwater extraction. To address this, a correction method was implemented in the visualization and analysis tool, enabling the reconstruction of the undisturbed subsurface temperature field from the measured log temperatures and inflow fluxes along the borehole (Fig. 5b).

In this approach, the advective rise of deep warm water from the bottom-hole temperature, as well as its cooling caused by inflowing colder water along the well, are described by

$$q^{up} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = q^{in} (T^* - T) + \alpha (T^* - T) \quad (1)$$

where q^{in} is the inflow rate ($q = q(z)$) and α is a conductive exchange term, which is often negligible ($\alpha = 0$). The upward flow rate q^{up} increases with the cumulative inflow along the well $q^{up} = \sum_{z \text{ below}} q^{in}$.

The procedure is to iteratively adjust the subsurface temperature T^* (grey line in Fig. 5b) such that the resulting temperature profile T (black line), calculated from the steady-state heat transport equation (1), matches the observed log temperature (red line). A prerequisite for this approach is that inflow zones (marked blue in Fig. 5b) and rates along the borehole are known, which is the case for about 30% of wells in the dataset from Rhineland-Palatinate. In total, only a small number of logs were finally corrected. The main advantage is that temperature logs recorded during groundwater extraction can now be included in the analysis, for instance to compare logs measured during shut-in and pumping conditions. This enhances confidence in the data and provides a basis for further quality assessment.

4.3 Effect of topography and urbanization

The best-fit line using only land surface elevation for the Baden-Württemberg dataset shows considerable scatter (Fig. 2b), suggesting that additional factors influence near-surface temperatures. Since shallow subsurface temperatures are known to be affected by land use (Bayer et al., 2016), the effect of surface sealing was evaluated for the Rhineland-Palatinate dataset.

Fig. 6 Effect of topography and urbanization on shallow temperatures in Rhineland-Palatinate a) Relation between 50 m subsurface temperature and elevation with dependence on surface sealing (colours denote main geological units); b) Hillslope representation of temperature logs arranged by elevation, including the degree of surface sealing.

A multiple linear regression was performed with both land surface elevation and surface sealing as predictors. Outliers were removed using the 1.5 × interquartile range criterion (6–14.7 °C), reducing the 50 m depth data points from 260 to 250. As a result, the R^2 increased slightly from 0.43 to 0.45, indicating that accounting for surface sealing reduces the scatter of temperatures around the regression line. Surface sealing in the dataset ranges from 0 to nearly 100 percent, leading to a temperature difference of approximately 1 K (Fig. 6a). While the influence of urbanization was expected, this analysis highlights its magnitude relative to that of land surface elevation.

Figure 6b shows a hillslope representation of the temperature logs and relevant parameters. Warmer temperatures are clearly more frequent at lower elevations. Logs affected by surface sealing in these lower-elevation regions are found, for example, in Ludwigshafen and Worms (Upper Rhine Graben, black in Fig. 6a). In the Triassic Palatinate region (orange in Fig. 6a), logs impacted by sealing are mainly located around Kaiserslautern and Ramstein.

Abb. 7: Kriging interpolation using best-fit line (including shallow geothermal gradient) as external trend: a) Variogram for residual temperature (deviation from trend); b) Temperature at 50 m depth; c) Drift (trend) temperature; d) Residuals (crosses mark well locations).

The temperature pattern at 50 m depth, derived from Kriging interpolation using land surface elevation and sealing as external trends, primarily reflects topography, with an additional influence of surface sealing (Fig. 7). Elevated temperatures are observed particularly in and around Glückstadt and Monsheim in the Mainz Basin (red geological unit in Fig. 6a), likely due to upward flow of warmer water along faults. Temperatures above the trend are also in the eastern part of the Palatinate Forest, transitioning to the Upper Rhine Graben, whereas temperatures are below the trend in most other parts of the Palatinate Triassic region (orange unit). Additional temperature maxima occur in the Middle Rhine Graben (purple unit) and the volcanic region Lake Laach (brown unit in previous Fig. 6a).

Figure 8 finally shows a zoomed view of the Kriging-interpolated temperature field in an area of variable land use (Ramstein area). The impact of surface sealing is clearly visible with the temperature range reduced to highlight local variations. Southern parts are cooler due to higher elevation and temperatures are slightly below the trend, while the Kriging standard deviation remains below 1 K at locations with boreholes (Fig. 8c). The results emphasize the dominant role of topography, although surface sealing also has a noticeable effect.

Abb. 8: Zoomed view of the Kriging-interpolated shallow temperature field with variable land use (Ramstein area, reduced temperature ranges): a) Temperature at 50 m depth; b) Uncertainty; c) Drift (trend) temperature; d) Residuals (crosses mark well locations).

5. Summary and Conclusions

Temperature fields were derived using two complementary approaches: (1) extrapolation of satellite-based land surface temperatures with bottom-hole temperatures, and (2) independent analysis of temperature logs, supported by a dedicated visualization and analysis tool developed and refined for this purpose.

The first approach was demonstrated using the dataset from Baden-Württemberg, and the second with data from Rhineland-Palatinate. Both datasets are extensive, comprising temperature logs from about 1,200 and 360 wells, of which 480 and 260, respectively, were included in the analysis focused on a reference depth of 50 m.

A procedure was introduced to include operational and post-operational well logs in the evaluation, which was previously limited to shut-in logs. This allows to match multiple logs from a single borehole as a quality control measure. The quantitative impact of this procedure, as well as additional quality criteria, still requires further assessment.

Topography represents the most prominent large-scale trend in both datasets. In Baden-Württemberg, approximately 30% of the variability in temperatures at 50 m depth can be explained by a linear fit to land surface elevation ($R^2 = 0.30$). In Rhineland-Palatinate, more than 40% of the variability observed in logs at the same depth can be explained by such a fit. The R^2 value increases slightly from 0.43 to 0.45 when surface sealing is included as an additional explanatory variable in a multiple linear regression. The analysis indicates that temperatures in highly sealed areas are typically about 1 K higher. Notably, the slope of the linear fit to land surface elevation is close to the atmospheric lapse rate (≈ 6 K/km) at very shallow depths and increases with depth, reflecting both near-surface cooling with elevation and additional subsurface effects.

Overall, the surface-to-subsurface extrapolation approach, based on land surface and bottom-hole temperatures, can be regarded as an efficient first-step method for estimating large-scale temperature fields (e.g., at the national scale). Regions of interest can subsequently be refined through detailed temperature log analysis, as demonstrated for Rhineland-Palatinate.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the project WärmeGut (funding code 03EE40461), funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK). The authors gratefully acknowledge the Geological Surveys of Baden-Württemberg (LGRB) and Rhineland-Palatinate (LGB-RLP) for providing extensive and well-documented datasets as well as their kind and helpful support.

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